

Supplemental Information of:

Historical changes in seasonal aerosol acidity in the Po Valley (Italy) as inferred from fog water and aerosol measurements

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Section S1. Ammonia measurements and estimations

S1.1 Instrument and QA/QC procedure for gaseous ammonia measurements

The instrument is a commercial monitor based on the chemiluminescence principle of N-oxides detection with an external NH₃ converter. The measurement is following a standard certified QA/QC procedure (ISO9001:2015). It is calibrated for NO with a LAT certified cylinder (i.e. verified by the certified laboratory ACCREDIA, ISO17025) every 3 months (or every time there is a failure). The instrument performs a daily measurement of zero and span for NO (i.e. a constant measurement with a certified cylinder present in the cabin). If the parameters are not within the range of acceptability (+/- 4 zero, +/- 10% span), the maintenance and a new calibration with the NO cylinder (LAT) are performed. Once a year, calibration is also performed with a certified ammonia cylinder.

S1.2 Test on Deviation saturation ratio (D_r) in estimating gaseous ammonia from fog-water composition and pH

Ricci et al. (1998), investigating the uptake of soluble gases by fog droplets, documented empirical large deviations from theoretical Henry's law equilibrium in this kind of system. In order to account for these deviations, we applied a specific Deviation saturation-ratio (D_r) to the theoretically calculated $NH_{3(fog)}^{eq}$ atmospheric concentrations.

Considering the fundamental weight of this deviation for the estimation of $NH_{3(fog)}$ and the consequent assessment of the aerosol pH from fog data, we investigate carefully here the possible corrections that should be applied to the theoretically calculated $NH_{3(fog)}^{eq}$.

Given that our analysis refers to bulk composition of fog water (in which we cannot keep track of size and pH of the single droplets), actually the Deviation ratio (D_r) can change depending on the duration and characteristics of the fog-event (as hypothesized and measured by Pandis and Seinfeld, 1991 and by Ricci et al. 1998). However, using the available concurrent measurements it is possible to estimate the range of possible D_r values at least for the last 2 years of our dataset. Rewriting eq. (5) in the main text as follows:

$$\log_{10} \frac{NH_{3(fog)}}{NH_{4(fog)}^+} = \text{pH} - \log_{10} \text{LWC}_f - \log_{10} \left(\frac{H_{NH_3} * K_{a1} * RT}{K_w} \right) \quad (5b)$$

a regression of the two terms of the equation can be made with the experimental data and ranges for the regression intercept "c" can be derived. Consequently, D_r values can be calculated ($c = \log_{10} D_r$). Figure S1 shows the range of this parameter for measurements available over two years (2017-2018).

Figure S1. Regression of the two terms of Eq. (5b). Color scale corresponds the pH of fogwater samples. Grey lines correspond to different D_r values calculated.

Our analysis highlights (as expected) that D_r can vary substantially across fog-events (mostly between 0.08-3.16 with a mean value of 0.5) and that there is a relationship between D_r and the pH of the aqueous solution (color-scale in Figure S1).

Following the definition of D_r (Section 3.2 of the main text), we can rewrite Equation (5b) and express D_r in terms of the measured fogwater pH, liquid water content and $\frac{\text{NH}_3(\text{fog})}{\text{NH}_4^+(\text{fog})}$:

$$D_r = 10^{\left[\left(\log_{10} \frac{\text{NH}_3(\text{fog})}{\text{NH}_4^+(\text{fog})} \right) - \left(\text{pH} + \log_{10}(\text{LWC}_f H_{\text{NH}_3} \frac{K_{a1}}{K_w} RT) \right) \right]} \quad (6b)$$

Figure S2 (blue dots) shows a plot of the D_r calculated in this way as function of fogwater pH from the available $\text{NH}_3(\text{g})$ observed data (referring to the last 2 years of the fog dataset). Fitting these available values (using a parabolic function, with R^2 of 0.83, blue line), allows us to extend the evaluation of D_r as function of fog water pH along all the 25-years dataset, as shown in Figure S2 (orange dots).

Figure S2. Deviation ratios (D_r) calculated from Equation 6b. Blue dots and line show D_r expressed in terms of fogwater pH, from the available measurements (referring to 2017-18 samples) and the corresponding parabolic curve fit to the data. Orange dots represent the values of D_r predicted by the parabolic fit to the whole 25-years fogwater dataset.

We then evaluate the D_r fit in 2 ways:

(a) Comparing the degree to which it can reproduce the observed ammonia concentrations measured ($\text{NH}_{3(\text{obs.})}$) from fog-water composition and pH ($\text{NH}_{3(\text{fog})}$) (section 3.2 of the main text) using fixed values of D_r (0.5, 1.0) and the fit from Figure S2. The scatter plots in Figure S3 show this comparison for both the estimation of gaseous ammonia concentrations and the total-Ammonium ($=\text{NH}_4^+(\text{p})+\text{NH}_3(\text{g})$), which is the value actually used as ISORROPIA-II input. The superiority of the fit over fixed values of D_r is clear.

Figure S3. Comparison between atmospheric ammonia (panel a) and total-ammonium (panel b) concentrations ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) measured and retrieved from fog-water composition and pH (using the theoretical aqueous-phase equilibria as described in section 3.2 of the main text). Different Deviation saturation-ratios (D_r) are tested in order to choose the best values considering the options suggested by our regression analysis and the measurements available ($D_r=1$ or 0.5 or $f(\text{pH})$). Solid black line represents the 1:1 line between observed and estimated data. In the sub-plots are zoomed the comparison between observed and estimated data as retrieved using D_r as function of the fogwater pH ($D_r=f(\text{pH})$) in order to highlight the correlation between the data.

(b) Comparing estimated $\text{NH}_{3(\text{fog})}$ with available measurements also in other places of the Po Valley, like Lombardy (where $\text{NH}_{3(\text{g})}$ is measured since 2003). The levels of ammonia in Lombardy are considered to be generally higher than in the eastern part of the Po Valley where SPC resides (Fig S2 in Van Damme et al., Nature 2018, doi: 10.1038/s41586-018-0747-1). We add here below (Figure S4) a graph showing the annual averages of NH_3 measured in different sites and estimated by fog water equilibrium at SPC. Using D_r calculated from the fog-pH (Figure S2) we obtain NH_3 concentrations not exceeding those at the Lombardy background site values (a rural background site, similar to what SPC is considered). In particular, the $D_r=f(\text{pH})$ corrects substantially the extreme concentrations corresponding to the middle years of our 25-years series (2003-2008) that are even higher than those recorded for locations directly impacted by husbandry activities in Lombardy (the ‘‘Lombardy hotspot’’ site in the figure).

Figure S4. annual averages of $\text{NH}_{3(g)}$ concentrations measured in different sites and estimated by fog-water equilibrium at SPC, uncorrected ($D_r=1$) and corrected using D_r calculated as function of fog-water pH ($D_r=f(\text{pH})$), respectively. Lombardy hotspot and background values refer to measurements carried out respectively at Corte De' Cortesi and Schivenoglia Air Quality monitoring stations (available at <https://www.dati.lombardia.it/> , by ARPAE Lombardia).

It is important to underline that the regression in Figure S2 is empirical and, while it is plausible that it can be applied in other studies as it is (especially if the fog has similar ambient temperature and microphysical characteristics – droplet number and liquid water content – with Po Valley fogs), confirmation should still be carried out with measured data prior to its use.

It is worth noting that fogwater pH resulted to be a major driver for D_r possibly because it determines the effective Henry Law coefficient which in turn can affect the kinetics of adsorption/desorption of condensable trace gases in cloud/fog water. Fog LWC and droplet size-distributions are deemed to be important as well, but the small fog droplet mean diameter (5 - 10 μm , Seinfeld and Pandis, 2016) is responsible for limited collision-coalescence and balance between production and deposition, making fog droplet size distributions less variable than for a cloud case. Because of the relatively constant size of fog droplets, the timescale of uptake (with the assumption that all droplets have roughly the same pH) would depend on the disequilibrium between gas and equilibrium vapor pressure - which is a strong function of cloudwater pH. More work needs to be done to help unravel the nuances to help generalize the correlation, but that would be a topic of a future study.

Apart from fog droplets, there is unactivated aerosol that participates in the equilibrium process (and with different pH than the droplets). But the amount of NH_3 uptake compared to that before the fog event is orders of magnitude less than that associated with the uptake of NH_3 by the fog droplets (this is because the liquid water content of interstitial aerosol is orders of magnitude less than that associated with fog water droplets). Therefore, the equilibrium NH_3 value, and departure from that, described by D_r , is driven by the gas-droplet equilibrium in-cloud.

All the above reasons confirm that the fogwater pH is the appropriate quantity to link to D_r .

Section S2. Evaluation dataset: observed vs estimated ammonia/ammonium concentrations

Figure S5. Evaluation dataset: comparison between ammonia ($\text{NH}_3(\text{g})$), ammonium ($\text{NH}_4^+(\text{p})$) concentrations measured (black markers) and predicted by ISORROPIA-II using the PM2.5 (red markers) and fog (green markers) measurements/estimations. Top 2 panels refer to prediction in which only the ammonium concentrations (in PM2.5 and fog-water) are used as input; bottom 2 panels refer to prediction in which the sum of ammonium (in PM2.5 and fog-water) and the gas-phase ammonia concentrations (measured or estimated by fog-water composition) are constrained.

Table S1: Comparison between the concentrations of the main ionic species measured in fog water (Fog) and aerosol (PM2.5) samples. Average values \pm standard deviations of all the available parallel samples (n=63) are reported.

	Na ⁺	SO ₄ ²⁻	NH ₄ ⁺	NO ₃ ⁻	Cl ⁻	Ca ²⁺	K ⁺	Mg ²⁺
Fog	0.30 \pm 0.48	2.29 \pm 1.7	3.66 \pm 2.6	9.87 \pm 9.05	0.62 \pm 0.53	0.30 \pm 0.36	0.16 \pm 0.18	0.04 \pm 0.04
PM2.5	0.07 \pm 0.07	1.77 \pm 1.07	3.26 \pm 2.02	8.17 \pm 5.93	0.26 \pm 0.27	0.14 \pm 0.08	0.27 \pm 0.2	0.02 \pm 0.01

Figure S6: Pie charts showing the speciation of main ionic composition in the fog water (FOG) and aerosol (PM2.5) samples

There is a general good agreement even if the concentrations of some species into the fog-water samples with respect to the PM2.5 are slightly overestimated. This is the case of Sodium (Na) and Chloride, and on some extent also of Sulfate (SO₄). However, the overestimation is minor and balanced among the species showing a pretty good agreement in term of their relative contributions to the total mass.

Section S3. Statistical analysis of the pH trend

As reported in the main text (Section 4.2), the variability of the aerosol pH during each year is remarkable as well as the variability among years. Given this high variability, we applied an interquartile-range rule (IQR) for determining and removing the possible outliers from the annual averages. The interquartile range is calculated subtracting the first quartile (Q_{25th}) from the third quartile (Q_{75th}) of each year of data: $IQR = Q_{75th} - Q_{25th}$. Then any value greater than $1.5 \times IQR + Q_{75th}$ or lower than $1.5 \times IQR - Q_{25th}$ is considered outlier and removed from the calculation of the annual pH average. The dataset loses in this way 27 data points from the initial 577 fog-water samples collected at SPC since 1993 (becoming so 550 in total), with a new seasonal median number of samples of 19 (in the range 3-35).

Figure S7 shows the box and whisker plot of all the data, while Figure S8 shows the comparison between the annual pH averages resulting from the IQR rule application against those from the complete dataset: using both all the data or the IQR rule results in a significant negative trend at a

95% and 99% confidence interval (p-value <0.05 & <0.01) respectively, according to the OLS regression method. The trend calculated using the IQR rule is chosen as the best estimation and is discussed in the main text. It shows a net reduction of aerosol pH of 0.6 units over the 25-year period.

Figure S7. Box and whisker chart of the Aerosol pH trends as calculated by ISORROPIA-II using all the fog-water dataset (black markers). Grey diamond markers are the annual average values. The ends of the whisker are set at $1.5 \times \text{IQR}$ above the third quartile ($Q_{75\text{th}}$) and $1.5 \times \text{IQR}$ below the first quartile ($Q_{25\text{th}}$). If the Minimum or Maximum values are outside this range, then they are considered outliers. However, in order to simplify the graph, only the Min and Max outliers are highlighted.

Figure S8. Aerosol pH trends as calculated by ISORROPIA-II using all the fog-water dataset (blue markers and lines) or the IQR method (red markers and lines). Markers are the annual average values of aerosol pH calculated ($\text{pH AerFOG} + \text{NH}_{3(\text{fog})}$). Error bars represent the standard deviations of the pH values for each year.

Section S4. $\text{NH}_{3(\text{fog})}$ estimation effect on AerFOG pH variability

Considering the importance of gaseous ammonia atmospheric emissions and concentrations in a region like Po Valley, characterized by intense agricultural and livestock activities (Riciardelli et al., 2017), the AerFOG pH variability linked with different gaseous ammonia concentrations is evaluated by a set of simulations in which we varied the approach to estimate the $\text{NH}_{3(\text{g})}$ data used to constrain the model. The pH simulation was done alternatively: retrieving the $\text{NH}_{3(\text{g})}$ concentration in equilibrium with the NH_4^+ dissolved in fog-water samples ($\text{NH}_{3(\text{fog})}$), using the theoretical aqueous-phase equilibria as described in Section 3.2 of the main text as it is (1) or correcting it for different Deviation ratios (D_r): (2) $D_r=0.5$ (the average D_r value calculated in Supplementary Section S1) constant along the whole 25-years series; (3) D_r calculated as function of fog water pH ($D_r=f(\text{pH})$) as described always in Section S1; and finally (4) applying the available measured average ratio $\text{NH}_4^+(\text{p})/\text{NH}_{3(\text{g})}$ (using the available 2017-2018 dataset) and extending the same fixed ratio to all the fog-water samples. Figure S9 shows the results of these different approaches on the AerFOG pH trend.

The correction of the estimated $\text{NH}_{3(\text{fog})}$ for the empirical Deviation ratio defined in Section 3.2 and S1 has an impact in determining the aerosol pH which is only minor in term of average pH: with a concentration of estimated $\text{NH}_{3(\text{fog})}$ which is double when the correction is not applied ($D_r=1$ instead of 0.5), the aerosol pH results to be only 0.24 ± 0.07 units higher on average. For the other approaches the acidity results on average in a general good agreement: pH variations with respect to the uncorrected version (1) are -0.23 ± 0.27 and -0.22 ± 0.48 for the approach (3) ($D_r=f(\text{pH})$) and (4) ($\text{NH}_{3(\text{fix}=32\%)}$), respectively.

The pH trends calculated with the different $\text{NH}_{3(\text{g})}$ estimation approaches have in any case negative slopes even if with different reduction rates. In this context the $\text{NH}_{3(\text{fog})}$ theoretical approach represents a lower limit of the possible reduction trend (with a reduction rate of 0.02 pH units per year) while the upper limit is represented by $\text{NH}_{3(\text{fix}=32\%)}$ (with a reduction rate of 0.04 pH units per year).

Figure S9. Aerosol pH annual average values calculated by ISORROPIA-II using different $\text{NH}_{3(\text{g})}$ estimations as input: (1) retrieving the $\text{NH}_{3(\text{g})}$ concentration in equilibrium with the NH_4^+ dissolved in fog-water samples (using the theoretical aqueous-phase equilibria as described in section 3.2), blue markers and lines; (2) using a constant $D_r=0.5$ correction to the theoretical equilibrium ($\text{NH}_{3(\text{fog})}$ (corr., $D_r=0.5$)), green markers and lines; (3) using a correction D_r calculated as function of fog water pH ($\text{NH}_{3(\text{fog})}$ (corr., $D_r=f(\text{pH})$), red markers and lines); (4) applying the available measured average ratio $\text{NH}_4^+(\text{p})/\text{NH}_{3(\text{g})}$ (using the 2017-2018 PM_{2.5} and $\text{NH}_{3(\text{g})}$ measurements) and extending the same fixed ratio to all the fog-water (NH_3 fixed(32%)), black markers and lines. Error bars represent the standard deviations of the annual values.

Section S5. Fog-pH measurement effect on AerFOG pH variability

Fog pH measurements have an associated uncertainty that can potentially affect our thermodynamic analysis: in particular the pH is temperature dependent and so pH measurements performed in the laboratory can be biased with respect to the field.

To check if the uncertainty associated with the fog-pH measurements can affect the estimation of $\text{NH}_{3(\text{fog})}$ concentrations and consequently of the AerFog pH, we performed a set of simulations in which we varied the observed fog-pH of ± 0.5 and ± 0.2 units alternatively. This range of possible variability is set based on some tests we made in laboratory on a subset of fog samples (5 samples, tests repeated 3 times for temperature dependence: these tests demonstrate that depending on the temperature of the fog sample the fog-pH measure can vary with a maximum rate of $0.01 \text{ pH}/^\circ\text{C}$ (usually less, as showed in Figure S10).

Figure S10: fog pH variation as function of the fog water temperature. Markers and lines of different colors represent 5 different fog samples collected during the last month (November 2020).

The markers are the observed data points (mean of 3 different observations) at different temperature, while lines are the fitting lines of these points. The pH variations are calculated subtracting the intercept of the fitting line at 0°C to each fog pH measurement. Error bars represent the standard deviations of the 3 repeated measurements.

Considering that in the field the samples are collected only when the T is $>1^\circ\text{C}$ (to avoid instrumental damages due to the ice formation) and that the laboratory is kept at fixed $T=18\text{-}20^\circ\text{C}$, we can hypothesize a maximum T change of 20°C and so a maximum variability in fog water pH due to T of ± 0.2 units. In order to account for any other possible source of uncertainty in the fog-pH determination we performed in any case tests also changing the fog pH by ± 0.5 units. Results of these

tests on AerFog pH are reported in Figure S11, showing that fog water pH is not so influent on $\text{NH}_3(\text{fog})$ and aerosol pH estimation if we use the approach based on the D_r calculated as function of fog pH (as described in the new Supplementary Section S1) to correct the $\text{NH}_3(\text{fog})$. In particular, increasing/decreasing fog-pH of ± 0.5 units (which is already an overestimation of the possible range of fog-pH variation due to T of the solution, based on our tests) leads to change of the aerosol pH of max ± 0.1 units (on average). This result demonstrates the robustness of our estimations of aerosol pH and confirms what we state in the manuscript, i.e. that the pH of the aerosol is determined by variables other than those that determine the fog pH.

Figure S11: aerosol pH trends calculated by ISORROPIA-II varying the starting fog-pH necessary for the estimation of ammonia in equilibrium with fog ($\text{NH}_3(\text{fog})$). Red markers are the annual average values of aerosol pH calculated by ISORROPIA-II starting from the observed fog ionic composition and pH as input (pH AerFOG+NH3(pHfog_Obs)). Blue, gray, orange and yellow markers are the annual average values of aerosol pH calculated by ISORROPIA-II starting from fog ionic composition and fog-pH changed of ± 0.2 and ± 0.5 units respectively. Error bars represent the standard deviations of the calculated pH values.

Section S6. Trends of pollutants and meteorological parameters

Figure S12. Observed/estimated pollutants trends in the last 25 years: each panel shows the annual average values of concentrations (expressed as $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) measured or estimated from the fog-water. For the $\text{NH}_3(\text{g})$ estimation refer to the main text (section 3.2) and to Supplementary Section S1.

Figure S13. Observed meteorological trends in the last 25 years: annual average values of Relative Humidity (RH) and Temperature (T, expressed in Kelvin) regarding only the foggy days are reported. Panel a) shows the daily mean values. Panel b) instead the values integrated on the fog-sampling time periods.

It seems that the observed relative humidity integrated on the fog-sampling time periods show a sharp change in around 2006. Before 2006, RH was closed to 100%. After that, RH decreased to about 95%. One hypothesis is that the recorded decreasing RH associated to fog events is related to the increasing frequency of intermittent fogs (dense fog events interrupted by periods of less dense fog or no-fog). This is consistent with the reduced LWC of the fogs at SPC documented by Giulianelli et al. (2014) and with the changes in the frequency of days with good visibility in Italy in the period 1951-2017 documented by Manara et al. (2019). Another possible explanation can be the high uncertainty associated with measurements of RH close to 100% (like those recorded during fog events). But this uncertainty cannot explain the decreasing trend along time. There was actually a change in the thermometer used in 2007, but the RH was decreasing before 2007 and continued to decrease later, so this cannot explain the change. The uncertainty related to RH measurements during fog-events was another reason for which we decided to use the daily average of RH to calculate the aerosol pH with ISORROPIA: daily mean values are less affected by possible instrumental failures or artefacts.

S7. Meteorological variability effect and RH sensitivity test

Figure S14. Aerosol pH annual average values calculated by ISORROPIA-II using different relative humidity and temperature as input: the daily mean of the day in which fog occurred (orange circles) or the mean of the fog sampling period (corresponding to the maximum RH, minimum T of the day).

Figure S15. Aerosol pH and liquid water content (W_i) annual average values calculated by ISORROPIA-II using different fixed perturbed values of RH as input, decreasing from 99% until 70% (-5% steps). Panel a) and c) show the time series: the slope of the linear fit is reducing for reduced RH. Panel b) and d) highlight the differences between the pH calculated using the RH measured during fog sampling periods and the perturbed values.

Section S8. Drivers of aerosol pH reduction

Table S2. Multiple regression of pH with the variables used by ISORROPIA-II to calculate it: NH_4^{TOT} (gas+particle phase), NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} , Cl^- , K^+ , Na^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , RH and T. The regression is applied to the annual means. The contribution to R^2 for each of the independent variables is the decrease in R^2 with that variable omitted. The sum of individual contributions of R^2 are adjusted to equal the total R^2 . Relative contributions are calculating normalizing for the sum.

		AerFOG+NH3 pH	
		Total R^2	0.72
			Contr.to R^2
			Relative contr.
Main ions	SO_4^{2-}	0.12	17%
	NH_4^{TOT}	0.25	35%
	NO_3^-	0.02	2%
	Cl^-	0.05	7%
NVC	Na^+	0.01	1%
	Ca^{2+}	0.08	11%
	K^+	0.00	0%
	Mg^{2+}	0.03	4%
Meteo	RH	0.11	16%
	T	0.05	7%

Section S9. Aerosol pH seasonality in Po Valley

Table S3. Wintertime averages of Temperature (T) and Relative Humidity (RH) daily mean values considering alternatively all the days from November to March of each year (“all winter” columns) or only the days in which a fog-event occurs (“foggy days” columns)

Wintertime average of daily mean values				
	all winter		foggy days	
	T (°C)	RH (%)	T (°C)	RH (%)
1993	3.1	86	4.6	93
1994	5.2	91	5.5	92
1995	4.2	87	5.4	93
1996	5.4	89	3.4	94
1997	5.2	89	4.6	92
1998	4.2	85	4.1	97
1999	3.1	85	4.9	95
2000	4.6	88	5.7	94
2001	3.5	87	5.3	94
2002	5.4	89	5.4	94
2003	4.1	85	7.5	91
2004	4.2	90	3.9	98
2005	2.9	84	2.1	95
2006	2.2	85	6.6	90
2007	4.4	83	5.0	97
2008	5.4	86	5.2	91
2009	4.5	86	5.5	91
2010	4.0	88	7.8	87
2011	4.2	85	4.0	92
2012	3.0	83	5.2	84
2013	4.6	84	4.1	90
2014	7.6	88	7.7	91
2015	5.3	87	4.9	92
2016	5.4	86	5.7	91
2017	4.1	83	6.4	91
2018	5.3	86	5.9	88

Aiming to the best estimation of PM_{2.5} pH based on available measurements, we calculated the NH₃(obs) seasonality, considering the measurements carried out during the period Aug.2017-Dec.2018. We see on average a higher concentration of NH₃ during summer and the warmer seasons, as reported in Figure S13 (panel a) below. This seasonality is actually expectable due to the increasing agricultural activity and higher T for volatilization in warmer seasons. We calculated then also the monthly averages (Figure S13, panel b) and we added them to NH₄⁺ PM_{2.5} concentration to have the total ammonium to be used as input for ISORROPIA. In this way we have a comprehensive estimation of the pH for all the PM_{2.5} 2011-18 series.

a) **Figure S16:** NH₃(obs) seasonality, considering the measurements carried out during the period Aug.2017-Dec.2019. Markers and error bars represent the NH₃(g) mean values and standard deviations of each season. Winter=Dec.+Jan.+Feb. Spring=Mar.+Apr.+May. Summer=Jun.+Jul.+Aug. Fall=Sep.+Oct.+Nov.

We then reported the seasonality of the PM_{2.5} pH in comparison with the AerFOG pH in Figure S14. Based on this pH PM_{2.5} evaluation, we also elaborate Figure 5 in the main text.

Figure S17. Seasonality of aerosol pH as calculated by ISORROPIA-II from PM_{2.5} samples (in red) and fog samples (in blue) of the last 7 years of data (2011-2018). Markers and error bars represent the pH mean values and standard deviations of each season. The pH values are calculated without constraining gaseous ammonia because of the lack of such measurements.

Additional References

Manara, V., Brunetti, M., Gilardoni, S., Landi, T.C., Maugeri, M., 2019. 1951–2017 changes in the frequency of days with visibility higher than 10 km and 20 km in Italy. *Atmos. Environ.* 214, 116861 (doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2019.116861)

Seinfeld J.H. and Pandis S.N., *Atmospheric chemistry and physics – from air pollution to climate change*, John Wiley & Sons, New York, ISBN: 978-1-118-94740-1, 2016.